

5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials

D7.3 Technical management handbook v1.0

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Glossary of Terms and Abbreviations Used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	The 5th generation of mobile technology
5G-PPP	The 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
5G-ROUTES	5 th Generation Connected and Automated Mobility Cross-Border EU Trials
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application programming interface
CAM	Connected and automated mobility
CCAM	Cooperative, connected and automated mobility
CICD	Continuous integration continuous delivery
C-ITS	Cooperative intelligent transport systems
CM	Commercialization Manager
CN	Core network
CNF	Containerized Network Function
CNIS	Ericsson Cloud Native Infrastructure Solution
COTS	Commercial off the shelf
CP	Control plane
DN	Data network
D&CM	Dissemination and Communication Manager
E2E	End-to-end
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EDGE/MEC	Mobile network edge/Mobile edge computing
EO	Ericsson Orchestrator
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EVNFM	Evolved VNF Management
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

GeA	General Assembly
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
IM	Innovation and IPR Manager
IoT	Internet of things
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual property rights
I&CB	Innovation & Commercialization Board
KPI	Key performance indicator
LIDAR	Light detection and ranging
MANO	Management and orchestration
MNO	Mobile network operator
N3IWF	Non-3GPP Interworking Function
NF	Network function
NFV	Network functions virtualization
NFVO	Network functions virtualization
NGC	Next Generation Core
NLS	Network Location Service
NR	New Radio
NRF	Network Resource Function
NSA	Non-standalone
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NTN	Non-terrestrial network
OSM	Open source MANO
PA	Project architecture
PC	Project Coordinator
PDN	Packet data network
PDU	Protocol data unit
PM	Project Manager
PMB	Project Management Board
PoP	Point-of-presence

PTD	Prior to deadline
QoE	Quality of Experience
QRM	Quality Assurance and Risk Manager
RAN	Radio access network
RM	Risk management
RRM	Radio resource management
RTK	Real-time kinematic
SA	Standalone
SBA	Service-based architecture
SDN	Software defined network
SSC	Session and service continuity
TM	Technical Manager
ToC	Table of contents
TWP	Tenant Web Portal
UC	Use case
UE	User equipment
UP	User plane
UPF	User Plane Function
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VIM	Virtualized infrastructure manager
VM	Virtual machine
WP	Work package

1 Executive Summary

The current document serves as a practical guideline outlining the procedures essential for the effective technical management of the 5th Generation Connected and Automated Mobility Cross-Border EU Trials (5G-ROUTES) project for all the partners and participants. It provides a concise overview of the project and its general governance, including the organizational structure and the associated management processes. However, the focus of this deliverable is aimed at specifying and describing the core functions of technical management. These functions include not only general tasks, such as monitoring of technical progress, but also extend to more detailed responsibilities, such as managing platforms and environments for information exchange and processing. Additionally, this document provides a bundle of supporting materials critical for the members of the consortium. Among this material is the initial version of the project architecture (PA).

The underlying idea behind the technical management handbook is twofold:

- to assure that all the deliverables produced within the 5G-ROUTES project, are technically sound and of uphold quality. This deliverable will also provide mitigating guidance for any significant challenges that could arise during their preparation. This will be achieved by marking advice for the partners to report only the relevant information in an agreed format and in a timely manner.
- to streamline the project’s workflow by stating specific processes and fundamental agreements for all the partners to adhere to, ensuring a consistent understanding of basic principles across all tasks and underlying activities.

The information stated herein is aligned with D7.5 “Project Quality Handbook v1.0” and this document itself represents the initial version of the deliverable. The final version is due in M45.

2 Introduction

Effective technical management is crucial for the successful completion of the 5G-ROUTES project. To achieve the mentioned end goal, just as in any management endeavor, it necessitates specific rules and guidelines. The objective of this deliverable is to describe these guidelines from a technical management perspective in the form of a handbook.

The rules and guidelines have been tailored around the key technical players in the project – namely, Work Package (WP) leaders and the Technical Manager (TM). The handbook is meant to provide clear instructions on how specific tasks are to be performed while maintaining a certain degree of flexibility and agility. Naturally, this document is not exclusive aimed for to the aforementioned people, but it also extends to other roles within the project, with many of these roles assuming a supporting part in the context of this document.

2.1 Mapping 5G-ROUTES Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map 5G-ROUTES's Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal deliverable and task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 2. 1 Adherence to 5G-ROUTES's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	5G-ROUTES GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.3 Technical management handbook v1.0	Execution of overall technical management of the project.	Chapter 4	Chapter 4 specifies the core procedures through which the Technical Manager supports achieving the goals of the project.
TASKS			
T7.2 Technical Management	Monitoring of technical progress of the project.	Chapter 4	Chapter 4 discusses the subtasks of T7.2 in specific sub-chapters where applicable.
	Liaise with the External Advisory board (EAB) on technical matters.	Sub-chapter 4.3	The sub-section features an overview of how the EAB is used during the project and the next steps towards using their competences.
	Monitor technical deliverables.	Sub-chapter 4.4	Although the TM is ultimately responsible for monitoring the technical deliverables, a supporting method for creating, submitting and monitoring the technical deliverables has been introduced in the form of a detailed process. With each step of the process, a responsible entity has been identified.
	Provide a platform for information exchange.	Sub-chapter 4.5	The sub-chapter identifies all the environments used within the project to store, process and exchange data.

	Handle issues like knowledge management.	Sub-chapter 4.5	Knowledge management has been considered a part of overall data management.
	Prepare technical reviews.	Chapter 4	No specific section has been created for this component. It is suggested that the TM supports the consortium through a wide range of activities, out of which, creating technical reviews or any other kind of materials is just one.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Following the introduction in Chapter 2, Chapter 3 of this document presents a summary of the project, including the timeline and dependencies. Additionally, the same chapter presents a general management structure of the 5G-ROUTES project to familiarize the reader with all the entities and roles involved.

Chapter 4, which is the core chapter of this deliverable, offers a more detailed discussion regarding technical management with the specific core functions spread out under different sub-chapters.

Chapter 5 introduces key supporting materials for the members of the consortium to use throughout the project's duration. These include the communication processes, the project architecture, and a framework for performance measurement.

Chapter 6 brings the document to a close with conclusions.

2.3 Linkage to Other Project Outputs

Table 2. 2 D7.3 linkage to other deliverables

5G-ROUTES GA Component Title	Deliverable Chapter(s)	Contribution and Value of linkage
INPUTS from other deliverables utilised in this report		
D7.5 Project Quality Handbook v1.0	Sub-chapters 3.2 and 4.3	Sub-chapter 3.2 – introduce the general project management structure. Sub-chapter 4.3 – introduce the members and explain the necessity of the EAB.
D2.5 AI-based Positioning Enhancements for V2X v1.0	Sub-chapter 5.2.2	Support the project architecture description regarding location services.
D2.7 Tenant Web Portal Implementation and Deployment v1.0	Sub-chapter 4.5.2	Provide input regarding the Tenant Web Portal (TWP).

D2.9 Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0	Sub-chapters 4.5.5 and 5.2.2	Sub-chapter 4.5.5 - provide input regarding GitLab as the code repository for the project. Sub-chapter 5.2.2 – provide the list of technological enablers being developed presently within WP2.
D5.7 Data Management Plan v1.0	Sub-chapter 4.5.3	Provide input regarding Zenodo.
OUTPUTS from this report <u>utilised by other deliverables</u>		
Not specified	Chapter 4, 5	The procedures, guidelines and supporting materials described in Chapter 4 and 5 are applicable to all, mainly, technical deliverables and will be used during their preparation phase.

3 Project Overview

The successful implementation of a vast collaborative research and innovation project like 5G-ROUTES, demands the establishment of efficient, well-documented and structured project management procedures. These help to guarantee that there is a clear distribution of responsibilities between the project partners, the flow and exchange of information is done in a controlled manner, the production and verification of deliverables is solid, and the risks are identified and mitigated efficiently.

Beyond providing an overview of the project, the following subsections elaborate on the management structure of 5G-ROUTES. This structure is tailored to meet the needs of all the stakeholders, assuring that the required results are achieved for everyone involved.[1]

3.1 Project Summary and Objectives

5G-ROUTES constitutes a 5th generation mobile technology (5G) Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) Phase 3 project, and its primary objective is to validate, through robust evidence, the latest 5G features in the domain of the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) specifications (R.16), of connected and automated mobility (CAM) under realistic conditions. Specifically, 5G-ROUTES will conduct advanced large-scale field trials for the most representative CAM applications, to demonstrate seamless functionality across a prominent 5G cross-border corridor (specifically the Via Baltica North), spanning across 3 EU member states (Latvia-Estonia-Finland). The trials are aimed at facilitating the acceleration of wide-spread deployment of 5G end-to-end (E2E) interoperable CAM ecosystems and services in digitized motorways and shipways throughout Europe.[2]

The key objectives of the project include:

- to develop innovative and commercially exploitable CAM use cases (UC) for the automotive and the maritime sectors within the cross-border context.
- to analyze the technical and business requirements for these use cases, to enable extensive large-scale CAM field trials.
- to advance and optimize the enabling technologies, integrating artificial intelligence (AI) for the reliable, seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable CAM services across borders.
- to leverage and upgrade key assets from previous results and commercial products, to integrate the technological enablers in an end-to-end CAM ecosystem, to set up the 5G corridor and to facilitate lab and large-scale field trial validation.
- to demonstrate the potential and the user value in advanced CAM deployments at cross-border areas, by characterizing and optimizing 5G technologies at both lab tests and large-scale trials.
- to develop and validate the business models of advanced CAM use cases and protect the European Union (EU) intellectual property (IP).
- to provide rationalized contribution to key standardization bodies within the CAM context.
- to ensure long-term success through wide dissemination of the project's results and to exploit synergies with other 5G-PPP projects and 5G CAM initiatives. [2, 3]

One of the main challenges that the emerging 5G networks are facing, is to support the deployment of innovative applications for CAM. These applications need to seamlessly function when crossing borders, regardless of the mode of transport and whether passengers or cargo are involved. Multimodal considerations are equally key as evidenced through broad collaborations of EU member states and associated countries, the telecom industry, and stakeholders in automotive and other means of transport (e.g., maritime). The European Commission's (EC)

vision is to make the mobility of people and goods in the EU safer, cleaner, more efficient, ubiquitously connected, highly accessible and user friendly.

Compelling CAM enablement technologies are predicted to be based on:

- the evolution of digital technologies, such as the internet of things (IoT), artificial intelligence, high-performance computing and powerful 5G infrastructures.
- novel CAM services, such as automated driverless vehicles, yielding substantial business potential whilst significantly transforming the way citizens and goods move in the future.

The motivations behind CAM have far-reaching implications for environmental, demographic, social and economic aspects, as well as for increased road safety, traffic efficiency and driving comfort. Effective communication between vehicles, infrastructure and other road users is also crucial to increase the safety of future automated vehicles and their associated integration in the overall transport system. However, seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable CAM services at both national level and across internal EU borders necessitates the realization of large-scale cross-border pilots in a crucial 5G corridor of Europe. This is required to:

- validate the latest 5G technologies in ways that consider technical, business and EU policy factors for CAM.
- engage the 5G CAM community as co-dependent stakeholders to fine-tune and shape the future needs and requirements of CAM.

Moreover, to address the main challenges, the cross-border experiments need to target use cases beyond the cooperative intelligent transport systems (C-ITS) safety applications. These include automated cooperative driving, awareness driving, sensing driving, uninterrupted infotainment passenger services on the go and multimodal services. Hence, 5G-ROUTES will cover key use cases in these service categories through a comprehensive approach for addressing the CAM challenges. [3]

3.2 Organizational Structure and Management

To ensure the successful achievement of the project milestones and deliverables, specific responsibilities are allocated to 5G-ROUTES members and bodies. The project is managed following the logic depicted in Figure 3.1 with the key entities being:

- the General Assembly (GeA).
- the Project Management Board (PMB).
- work package leaders.

These entities receive additional support from the External Advisory Board, an Ethics panel and an Innovation & Commercialization Board (I&CB). The structure has been designed to: [4]ensure that the project meets its contractual obligations. This will entail continuous progress monitoring, managed by the Project Coordinator (PC), communication and a shared understanding of roles and responsibilities.

- facilitate the delivery of high-quality research and development. Central to achieving this will be the coordination of the activities of the technical partners and the integration of their results.
- maximize, measure, and validate the impact of the system on the target audiences, both within and beyond the technology enhanced learning research and industry communities.

Figure 3.1 5G-ROUTES Project Management Structure

General Assembly

This entity is led by the Project Coordinator and is assembled regularly at least once a year to make decisions regarding the project's overall strategy and contractual aspects. The GeA may also convene more often if needed. It is the highest decision-making authority in the consortium¹, which includes representatives from each partner, having the authority to make decisions on behalf of their respective organisations.

The GeA appoints the Ethics panel and the I&CB members and chairs. The typical meeting agenda includes:

- report by the Project Manager (PM).
- report by the Quality Assurance & Risks Manager (QRM) on quality and risks issues.
- reports by the WP leaders on technical implementation issues.
- approval of annual and final reports.
- approval of yearly implementation plans.
- decisions on specific items.

Project Management Board

The PMB manages the consortium between the General Assemblies. This includes technical matters, quality assurance, the consortium agreement, roles and responsibilities, audit certificates, ethics, gender issues, societal questions and contact with 5G-PPP and other third parties and the EU. The PMB brings to the project a wealth of experience in coordinating EU projects over many years and ensures that the project will achieve its objectives and satisfies the needs of the consortium, its stakeholders and end users. To achieve this, a mandate from the GeA has been provided during the project's kick-off meeting, assigning non-strategic project decisions to the PMB so that day-to-day actions (e.g., reallocation of resources and/or budget) can be taken in a timely manner without causing significant delays.[1], [4]

The PMB reports to the GeA, is chaired by the PC, and according to D7.5 "Project Quality Handbook v1.0", includes the following managers:

- **Project Coordinator – Ericsson**

The PC is responsible for the scientific management of the project, setting strategic directions, reporting and serving as the liaison with the EC. As the PC's organisation is a founding member of the 5G-PPP association, the PC will participate in 5G-PPP Steering Board activities. The PC ensures efficient communication between the

¹ Consortium members are listed in Annex I

partners and mediation of any conflicts if necessary. As chair of the GeA and PMB, the PC is responsible for the integration, cross-disciplinary issues of the project, for planning and for communication between the partners and the EU. The PC monitors the progress of the project's results and implements any necessary corrective measures. The PC also ensures any final reports submitted to the EU are complete and accurate. Additionally, they maintain team motivation, encourage creativity amongst partners and oversee all activities of the work in the project, in close cooperation with the Project Manager, Technical Manager and Commercialization Manager (CM).

- **Project Manager – Inlecom**

The PM manages the project, strongly collaborates with the TM and the CM and reports to the PC and ultimately the GeA. The PM monitors the project status and checks its progress against the agreed schedule (including budget and effort), also if milestones are met and deliverables produced in a timely manner. Additionally, the PM supports the PC with organizational procedures such as producing meeting agendas and minutes. Finally, the PM organizes resolution procedures regarding the issues in the consortium and liaises with other projects and initiatives.

- **Technical Manager – TTU & EEE**

The TM guides and monitors the technical progress of the project and coordinates the technical work across the relevant work packages. Also, the assessment of completed and running activities is amongst the responsibilities of the TM. In collaboration with the Project Manager, Commercialization Manager, Innovation and IPR Manager (IM), work package leaders and the External Advisory Board, the Technical Manager aligns the overall technical direction of the project with appropriate innovation strategies and establishes and maintains the 5G-ROUTES project architecture. The TM is also involved in the preparation and monitoring of the technical deliverables.

- **Innovation and IPR Manager – EBOS**

Leads the innovation and intellectual property rights (IPR) activities that identify and manage the innovation and intellectual property from the project as well as monitors all key innovation tasks. The IM advises the partners on the scope and potential of the innovation arising from the project and paying attention to discerning IP at regular checkpoints. The IM also identifies trends and technologies that could be of interest to the project and is responsible for the creation of the innovation progress reports for the EAB and the I&CB. The IM liaises with the CM.

- **Commercialization Manager – Inlecom**

Leader of the commercialisation activities of the project. The CM is responsible for all actions that promote the adoption of the project's results and solutions by end-users, identifying potential adopters and designing the overall go-to market strategy and commercialisation actions. In strong collaboration with the IM, EAB and I&CB, the CM is responsible for all activities towards market take-up, including showcases and the project's branding. The CM checks the progress regarding business objectives and performs the corresponding risk management. The CM leads the market assessment, feasibility study, revenue planning, business model and roadmap creation.

- **Dissemination and Communication Manager (D&CM) – CTTC**

Leads the dissemination and communication activities. The D&CM is responsible for defining the dissemination strategy for the consortium and organizing the dissemination and communication activities to maximise the project's wider adoption.

- **Quality Assurance and Risk Manager – ENIDE**

Guides and monitors the project's quality plan and assess the risks. Additionally, the QRM ensures the high-quality of deliverables and fully tested and reliable software systems. The QRM is the quality reviews' chair and performs project quality evaluation criteria, risk assessment, continuous monitoring, triggers quality assurance project reviews, assessment procedures, evaluation measurements and produces quality review reports. The QRM also supervises the implementation of a quality plan and organizes and supervises the quality review/peer reviews for all submitted deliverables. Lastly, the QRM alerts the PM on any pending quality issues for the project.

Work Package leaders

They are leaders of a given work package from WP1 to WP6 and report to the PM, who is also the leader of WP7. They produce detailed work plans and progress reports, guard the timely and effective execution of the WP work and that deliverables meet the quality standards. They control and monitor activities of tasks and regularly communicate, as needed, with task leaders. They manage the information flow with other WPs, monitor the WP plan and maintain consistency with the project plan. They review WP results and flag any underperformance. They provide input to management reports and represent the WP at the PMB.

External Advisory Board

1. The EAB comprises of a well-balanced group of external advisors drawn from across Europe. This composition ensures a well-rounded pool of expertise covering the project's focus areas. A more detailed discussion on EAB is in Section 4.3 of this document. The primary role of the EAB is to provide valuable input and guidance on many different areas (e.g. technological, market, ethical considerations) and this feedback will be taken into account to make any necessary and relevant amendments to the project.

Ethics panel

Chaired by the Legal & Ethics Leader (from TTU), it includes legal advisors of the participating members (experts on ethics, privacy, gender and legal issues). The role of the Ethics panel is to monitor the objectives and implications of the project's research, to ensure that it conforms to the highest ethical standards. The full list of the Ethics panel members is provided in D7.7 "Report on legal and ethics monitoring v1.0".

Innovation & Commercialization Board

Chaired by the Innovation Manager (from EBOS), it includes a member from each partner organisation engaged in the development of the technological enablers and in the field trials (ADSF, ATOS, CTTC, EBOS, ENIDE, CERTH, IQU, LMT, TTU, VTT, WINGS) and the Commercialization Manager. Their role is to specify in detail the commercialisation strategy and implement the process for filing patents.

3.3 Timeline of the Project

The 5G-ROUTES project will be executed over three continuous and sequentially aligned phases of development, as listed in Table 3.1 and illustrated in Figure 3.2. The proposed methodology aims to validate the project outcomes in relevant environments to expedite the rapid commercial take-up of its technology and network products.

Table 3.1 Summary of 5G-ROUTES project phases [8]

Phase 1 - Requirements, analysis, use cases and methodologies (M01-M04)
Phase 1 is concerned with methods for validating the 5G specifications and features, including the detailed analysis of the use cases and of corresponding technological (technical and service level) and business key performance indicators (KPI) for each use case, CAM deployment plans, testing methodologies for the cross-border collaboration on CAM testing, including the testing framework for the technological and business validation and the benchmarking of the results. Apart from the initial Phase 1, whose work has already started and incorporated into the architecture, the analysis will be extended until M24 to ensure that any new requirements that may arise because of the validation Phase 3, will be implemented as improvements in iterative testing of field trials.
Phase 2 – Component design, development, integration & testing in the lab (M05-M20)
Design and development of the 5G-ROUTES technological enablers for CAM services including the 5G infrastructure setup and operational readiness. Integration of all system components into an application framework and dry run testing to verify the correct communication between all vehicle-to-everything (V2X), railway and IoT elements and 5G testbed networks. Execution of lab trials in 4 different locations (Barcelona - CTTC, Tallinn - TTU, Tampere – VTT, Riga – EDI & LMT) to experiment with the use cases over different 3GPP releases and to ensure proper preparation and fine tune the enabling technologies for large-scale validation in field trials under realistic conditions along the 5G corridor.
Phase 3 – Validation in large-scale field trials & impact maximization (M21-M46)
The final phase is concerned with the establishment and setup of pilot sites in Finland, Estonia and Latvia and a 5G corridor for large-scale cross-border field trial validation. Iterative execution of 13 use cases in large-scale cross-border field trials over three consequential and iterative cycles of testing are planned in this phase. According to the recent project amendment draft (not approved by the EC at the time of writing this document) the first trial cycle took place in 2022 and used the 5G non-standalone (NSA) (3GPP R15) network. Due to the postponement of the roaming option and the selection of a new alternative Inter-PLMN workaround solution, all 2023 terrestrial site tests will be postponed to 2024. The second and third cycle will be performed within 2024 respectively, using the single 5G standalone (SA) (3GPP R16) network. Iteration is necessary to ensure that potential feedback improvements are applied to all ecosystem components thus enabling regression testing to ensure baseline target key performance indicators are met. Results from the first large-scale localized field trials deployment will be fed back into WP1, WP2 and WP3 for potential improvements prior to the second round of field trials. Further extended validation testing will be performed in large-scale field trials along the entire 5G corridor for verification of improvements in KPIs based on the developed methodologies in WP1. Phase 3 also includes dissemination, innovation, commercialization, standardization, capacity building and data management activities in WP5-WP6.

Continuous improvements within the 5G-ROUTES project will be achieved through feedback from the large-scale field trials, providing the basis for information sharing, operation, learning and improvement.

The timeline Gantt chart for 5G-ROUTES is depicted in Figure 3.2.

However, an updated Gantt Chart, with a proposition of 3-month extension, will be provided upon the finalization of the amendment that is currently discussed within the project Consortium.

3.4 WP Dependencies

As a reference point for the consortium members to identify and understand the cross-linked dependencies within the 5G-ROUTES project, Figure 3.3 has been created. It should be noted that:

- the dependencies will be updated to some extent throughout the duration of the project.
- there are other dependencies in the project, which are not specified in the following table and figure because these are out of the scope of the technical domain. In this case a more detailed description is given separately in specific deliverables.
- use cases provide horizontal input to all work packages and tasks, not only those shown in Figure 3.3.
- WP7 as the managing WP, covers all work packages and tasks.

The following table briefly lists the dependencies depicted in Figure 3.3.

Table 3. 2 Dependencies of tasks, use cases and work packages.

Output	Input	Brief description
UCs	T 1.1	Contribution on UCs analysis and requirements
UCs	T 3.4	Contribution on lab trials
UCs	WP 4	Contribution on field trials
WP 1	WP 4	Requirements for field trials
WP 1	WP 5	Contribution on business KPIs definition
T 1.1	T 1.2	Specifications and requirements of the use cases to develop the project deployment plan
T 1.1	T 3.1	Specifications and requirements of the use cases to develop the 5G network infrastructure
T 1.1	T 3.2	Specifications and requirements of the use cases to define the CAM infrastructure
T 1.1	T2.1, T2.2, T2.3, T2.4	Specifications and requirements of the use cases to develop enablers and the Tenant Web Portal ²
T 1.2	T 1.4	Project deployment plan and testing framework
T 1.2	T 3.1	Input on network planning based on the deployment plan and trial sites analysis
T 1.3	T 1.4	Lists of performance indicators for the cross-border trials and test methodologies proposed for data gathering
T 1.3	T 3.1	Lists of performance indicators for the cross-border trials and test methodologies proposed for data gathering
T 1.4	T 2.4	Definition of the procedures for collecting the data feeds from the 5G nodes, analysis in Tenant Web Portal
T 1.4	T 3.4	Data collection procedures for the use cases that will be tested during the lab trials
T 1.4	T 4.1	The assessment framework for the localized large-scale trials
T 1.4	T 5.2	Methodology for the identification of use cases with the highest commercialization potential
WP 2	T 4.1	Enablers' definition for field trials

² The Tenant Web Portal is discussed in detail in Section 4.5.2

WP 2	T 5.3	Input to the Innovation registry and patents
WP 2	T 6.1	Enablers' demonstration in dissemination activities
T 2.1	T 2.5	Description of the AI assisted cross-domain MEC and integration fabric for CAM services in relation to the 5G-ROUTES Platform ³
T 2.2	T 2.5	Description of the AI based end-to-end slicing optimization in relation to the 5G-ROUTES Platform
T 2.3	T 2.5	Description of the AI based positioning for V2X in relation to the 5G-ROUTES Platform
T 2.4	T 2.5	Description of the Tenant Web Portal implementation and deployment with the 5G-ROUTES Platform
T 2.5	T 3.2	Requirements and interfaces for the deployment of the enablers in the CAM infrastructure
T 2.5	T 3.3	Requirements and interfaces for the deployment of the enablers in the 5G infrastructure
T 2.5	T 3.4	Testing environment setup and overall 5G-ROUTES Platform definition to evaluate its performance
T 2.5	T 4.3	Enablers' validation in the trials
WP 3	WP 4	Deployment of 5G infrastructure and lab tests carried out as input to WP4 for large-scale trials readiness
T 3.1	T 3.3	5G infrastructure specification as input to T3.3 to integrate technological enab
WP 4	WP 5	Commercialization, innovation management and standardization based on large-scale field trials' results
WP 4	WP 6	Dissemination and communication activities based on the performed large-scale field trials
T 4.1	T 4.2	Planning of field trials
T 4.2	T 4.3	Lessons learned based on field trials' results
T 5.1	T 5.2	Collaboration on analysis of defined business models
T 5.1	T 5.3	Innovative business models' definition, collaboration between both tasks
T 5.2	WP 6	Support for the organisation of localised business workshops (joint dissemination/ business events)
T 5.4	T 6.3	Collaboration standardization working groups

³ The 5G-Routes Platform is discussed in Section 5.2.2

Figure 3. 3 Dependencies within the 5G-ROUTES project

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 951867

4 Core Functions of Technical Management

The following sub-chapters describe a set of activities to be followed for effective technical management within the 5G-ROUTES project. This ensures that the technical domain remains at a high standard and aligned with the rest of the project. At the forefront of this endeavor is the Technical Manager, who is responsible for the outcome of the activities in the technical domain. Initially the role of the TM was assigned to TELIA. However, following TELIA's withdrawal from the project, the TM role was handed over to TTU and EEE.

4.1 Technical Vision and Plan

According to Part B of the Grant Agreement, the vision of 5G-ROUTES is to position EU as a global leader, by accelerating the acceptance of CAM. This entails achieving fully autonomous, safer, cleaner, more traffic efficient, user friendly and reliable mobility. It also involves ensuring seamless and uninterrupted delivery of interoperable cross-border CAM services. This will be empowered by ubiquitous 5G coverage and by large-scale deployment of CAM in urban areas and along main transport paths throughout Europe. The latter one for 5G-ROUTES aligns with the EC's ambitious vision for CAM in a digital single market, supports the Commission's EU policy in CAM and corresponds with the strategic objectives of realizing an EU-scaled network comprising 5G cross-border corridors.

In brief, 5G-ROUTES has strategically targeted the crucial "Via Baltica North" 5G EU corridor for large-scale CAM field trials that involve road and maritime modes of transport, covering Latvia, Estonia and extending it to Finland via the Gulf of Finland. To address the diverse needs and challenges of CAM uptake and realize its vision, 5G-ROUTES will field trial a diverse set of 13 use cases that span beyond C-ITS, covering the automotive, infotainment and transport & logistics sectors, including shipping. The use cases cover applications in the context of complete connectivity-enabled ecosystems around passengers and cargo. They combine on one hand automotive transport and on the other, multimodal transport (including shipping). Each use case is associated with a specific set of requirements and network-level, service-level and business-level KPIs, that enable:

- automated vehicles empowered with 5G connectivity to physically move across borders safely and with as little service disruption as possible.
- passengers to enjoy information and entertainment services while on the move with as few interruptions and without glitches as possible.
- the tracking of large volumes of cargo whilst providing proactive and multimodal management of passengers and freight, even when alternating between different modes of transport and when crossing internal EU borders.
- After several changes in the project, it became evident that the railway part of the project is not relevant, hence it was removed from project scope, resulting in a reduction of number of use cases.

The vision of the TM is to enable the EC's plans for CAM through the efficient support within the 5G-ROUTES project. Given the challenges in deploying the 5G SA core thus far, the immediate plan of the TM is to have the 5G NSA network operational for the first round of field trials in the spring of 2022. In parallel, 2022 is also planned for the acquisition and deployment of the SA cores (for specific project partners) and the role of the TM here is to oversee and ultimately guarantee the successful completion of this process, preparing for the 2024 round of field trials. In September 2023, the new 5G SA core architecture (5.2.2) was finalised.

One of the key activities in deploying the SA cores is interfacing them with the enablers developed within the project. The connection to the 5G SA core network is done through the UPF component, and in addition, it is necessary to use an external router on the network operator side, which is necessary to select and direct requests from users either to the Internet, DNS service or the CAM platform, since UPF does not have this function. The latest version of the project architecture is discussed in Section 5.2.2 of this document.

Decidedly, it is the aim of the TM to oversee the production of consistent and high-quality deliverables within 5G-ROUTES, which is an ongoing task. Following a process, described in Section 4.4, the TM, along with other project partners, is heavily invested in integrating the information from different deliverables into the actual activities taking place across all the WPs.

4.2 Monitoring and Reporting of Technical Progress and Quality

First and foremost, the main role of the Technical Manager is to monitor and coordinate all the technical activities according to the contractual schedule. As the tasks in the project are performed in work packages, tight communication between the TM and WP leaders is crucial, mainly to coordinate but also to highlight issues. The technical management does not intrude into the daily operations of any work package in the sense that the responsibility of controlling and monitoring task specific activities, communicating with other WPs, monitoring the WP plan, and maintaining alignment with the overall project plan, falls on the shoulders of the WP leaders.

For 5G-ROUTES, the Technical Manager (together with the Deputy) coordinates and communicated activities in the technical domain in the following ways:

- meeting with the WP leaders on a bi-weekly basis to go over the WPs progress in as much detail as needed and bring any issues to the table. The Project Coordinator is also present during these meetings to speed up the information exchange between the TM and general project management.
- meeting with the PMB to discuss the status of the project and offer high-level advice on decision-making.
- having a weekly technical meeting with the project partners to unify the technical information and plan the next steps. This forum also often involves detailed technical discussions on matters requiring extensive input.
- meeting with the project architecture task force to discuss and form the final architecture⁴.
- adopting an open-door policy towards all the consortium partners. This means participating in specific discussions which are relevant to only one or a few partners.
- either preparing technical documents/presentations for meetings where these are needed or giving technical input for documents/presentations prepared by other consortium members. The mentioned meetings include both 5G-ROUTES internal and external.

It is the task of the TM to also be up to speed with the latest trends and developments around 5G which may have an impact on the project. Given that the position of Technical Manager encompasses both industry and academia (TTU and EEE), input from both sectors considered. Additionally, participation in the 5G-PPP Technology Board ensures the alignment of the 5G-ROUTES' technical domain with the broader European initiative.

The notions described above for monitoring technical progress within the 5G-ROUTES project are aligned with D7.5 "Project Quality Handbook v1.0".

⁴ - at the time of writing this deliverable, the initial version of the 5G-ROUTES project architecture has been finalized and this will be further enhanced in the course of 2022 as the 5G SA core will be deployed along with its functionalities and interfaces.

4.3 Liaising With the EAB

As per D7.5 “Project Quality Handbook v1.0”, the EAB comprises of a well-balanced group of external advisors who possess a wide range of knowledge that could be used to enhance the project’s focus areas. The EAB has members from many European countries, and it will offer impartial external advice from technological, scientific, market, regulation, ethical, societal, economic, and business points of view. [4]

In general, the consortium seeks to validate its technological direction with the EAB through consultations or through their participation at project GeA-s. Their feedback in several critical domains, is integral to the process of making any necessary adjustments or improvements to the project. A more detailed description of involving the EAB is described in both the GA and D7.5 “Project Quality Handbook v1.0”.

However, the 5G ROUTES project has faced certain technological challenges, e.g., lack of commercial networks, roaming capabilities, etc. that led to the need to refine the project’s scope. To this end, at the time of writing the updated version of this document (October 2023), the aforementioned challenges have impeded the full engagement of the EAB. Although the discussions with the EAB are considered to be more strategic than detailed, involving them from the technical management viewpoint is vital as the higher-level decisions regarding project outcomes will eventually translate into specific technical decisions, managed by the TM.

Despite these hurdles, the EAB will be approached to lend its expertise in advising the Consortium, particularly in the evaluation of recommendations and the validation process of the business models to be developed within the project and providing general support. To streamline with the ever-evolving landscape of the use cases and the relevant architecture, the PMB in collaboration with the WP leaders, conducted a review in order to adjust the representation within the EAB. This involved appointing individuals with expertise in maritime ecosystems and CAM service-related areas to ensure maximum support and alignment with the project's goals. Looking ahead, the EAB is expected to play a pivotal role in the upcoming workshops, that will be organised, focusing on business models validation. It will serve as a critical resource, offering valuable perspectives and expertise to help steer the 5G ROUTES project towards success in its technological, market, and ethical endeavours.

The way forward with involving the EAB, is as follows:

- keep the EAB members informed and engaged, by sharing project newsletters.
- Involve them in the evaluation of the recommendations coming out of T6.3 and participate in the business related workshops, organised as part of T5.2.

lastly, the EAB will be involved (either physically or through reporting via a written form) if the consortium has major issues/accomplishments to note.

4.4 Monitoring and Reviewing Technical Deliverables

Deliverable preparation in general for 5G-ROUTES, and thus the guidelines to assure quality output, are described in D7.5 “Project Quality Handbook v1.0”. Many updates to the quality handbook were made after the project interim review (June 2021) to increase, among other things, the role of the TM in quality assurance. The procedure outlined below, based on Figure 4.1, is tailored specifically for WP1-WP4, to guarantee technical excellence and soundness to the project. Figure 4.1 depicts not only the deliverable creation and submission timeline but also the responsible entities during each phase of the process, with a specific focus on the technical content of WP1-WP4.

The partner responsible for producing the deliverable (lead partner) must emanate from the principle that ensuring the quality of their document can be achieved following a procedure where:

1. at least 60 days prior to the deadline (PTD), the task of creating the deliverable will have been started. It is the responsibility of the task leader to kick-off the process and involve the necessary partners.
2. following the kick-off, the next immediate action is to draft a table of contents (ToC) and pitch (Pitch #1) this to the partners and the Technical Manager (in case of a technical deliverable). Based on the feedback, updates may have to be done to the ToC. Additionally, drafting the ToC will have to yield an understanding on the required input from other deliverables as well as the overall timeline for creating the deliverable together with the contributions from other partners. The main responsibility in this phase of the process lies with the task leader, however other partners, reviewers and a few project management entities are involved as well.
3. after completing the ToC comes the time to work on the deliverable, considering the contributions and inputs from other partners and deliverables. At this stage it is the responsibility of the task leader to compile the deliverable and the responsibility of others involved to contribute.
4. 40 days before the deadline, the initial version of the deliverable must be ready and submitted to the reviewers and the TM (in case of a technical deliverable). Prior to submission for review, the task leader must coordinate with the WP leader and get confirmation on the readiness of the deliverable. During review, effort from the TM and reviewers is required and they are responsible for the timely completion of the deliverable's assessment.
5. in parallel, in case the deliverable is a technical one, it must be submitted to the TM and to the project coordinator for additional assessment.
6. during the review phase, Pitch #2 will take place with the PC, TM, other partners and reviewers present. This is where the task leader has a final chance to comment on the content of the deliverable and the audience has a possibility to ask for clarifications and suggest modifications. The key responsibility again lies with the task leader but the TM and reviewers are in a crucial role as well.
7. at 20 days PTD and following Pitch #2, the task leader will get the final feedback from the reviewers and will incorporate the modification suggestions into the deliverable to compile its final version. It is the responsibility of the reviewers to submit the reviews on a specific template.
8. the penultimate step in the process starts at 10 days PTD when the QRM initiates a final quality check of the deliverable.
9. finally, the PC submits the deliverable on time to the European Commission.

4.5 Managing Environments for Data Storing, Processing and Exchange

For completing the 5G-ROUTES project successfully, many different environments/platforms for data storing, processing, and exchanging must be used. Most of these are widespread, like Microsoft 365 cloud-based solutions or Jira by Atlassian. These are used for basic activities such as data processing or teleconferencing, but also for project management or temporal assessment for specific tasks. It is the role of the TM in the project to know and consider all different data management platforms and make sure that the data processed using those is compatible, consistent, up to date and if needed, secure. The following sections present the different, 5G-ROUTES specific, data management environments.

4.5.1 TeamWork

A shared space, called TeamWork, has been set up to facilitate information exchange and file sharing between the project partners. TeamWork, illustrated in Figure 4.2, is an online tool, fully compatible with all the security and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements that can be used by the partners as the primary location for uploading and storing files related to the 5G-ROUTES project, such as deliverables, meeting minutes,

photos and other working documents. Access to TeamWork has been authorized for all project partners and no person outside the consortium can use it. The access rights are granted after confirmation with the Project Manager who supervises this tool. [1]

TeamWork will be the project's file repository and online collaboration platform during the project lifetime, and for up to 5 years after the end of the project for final closing activities after which the data will be permanently removed. More detailed information about TeamWork can be found in D7.5 "Project Quality Handbook v1.0".

Figure 4. 1 Deliverable submission process within the 5G-ROUTES project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 951867

Figure 4. 2 TeamWork environment

4.5.2 Tenant Web Portal

The Tenant Web Portal is the main user interface for the use case owners which will enable the graphical performance data presentation, and the web-based graphical front-end visualization environment for each of the metric parameters to be validated per UC scenario. [5]

More detailed information about the Tenant Web Portal, depicted in Figure 4.3, can be found in D2.7 “Tenant Web Portal Implementation and Deployment v1.0”.

Figure 4. 3 Tenant Web Portal

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 951867

4.5.3 Zenodo

Zenodo, which is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. Free to upload and free to access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable, and discoverable for the long term. [6]

Using Zenodo to make research data from 5G-ROUTES available to the research community at the end of the project, is a commitment made by the consortium, mentioned in D5.7 “Data Management Plan v1.0”.

Additionally, as the final datasets, public deliverables and publications will be transferred to Zenodo at the end of the project for sustainable archiving, the knowledge management will abide by the principles of discoverability, accessibility and availability also beyond the end of the project. For Zenodo, a 20-year lifetime for the program has been defined. [7]

4.5.4 Mailing lists

Group mailing addresses have been created for:

- the whole project.
- individual WPs.

CTTC is responsible for keeping the mailing lists of the project up to date by circulating them to project partners for validation every 6 months or through occasional requests for addition/removal. The full lists of email addresses included in different mailing lists are collectively included in a dedicated file, located on TeamWork.

4.5.5 Code Repository

GitLab, founded in 2011, started as an opensource project to help teams collaborate on software development. GitLab has since then turned into a complete DevOps platform delivered as a single application. This means that it comes with a built-in continuous integration continuous delivery (CI/CD) framework which enables teams to run automated tests quickly and for free. [8]

Regarding documentation hosting and versioning, GitLab offers a project-level Wiki which has its own internal history of changes. This is a great advantage since documentation updates do not necessarily require a new release, as it can be updated during the development timeline. The Wiki is a great feature for hosting user guides, trouble shootings, contribution guidelines and even changelogs and future work for a project. It is therefore selected to serve as a living document of the latest version of an enabler where UCs that plan to use its features may find a clear guide on how to do so.

5G-ROUTES will make use of GitLab to host the complete collection of enablers and other developments which may arise from the project. One of the immediate advantages, as compared to other alternatives, is to have everything integrated under the same tool: GitLab source code management, role-based access control, issues, documentation, a DevOps approach, and a full-fledged CI/CD framework. GitLab even provides a registry for each project which can be used to store containers, python wheels and other artefacts.

For 5G-ROUTES, the platform has been created in GitLab.com in the form of a Group which is called “5G-PPP-5G-ROUTES” as depicted in Figure 4. 4. This group has been made public however the developed enablers are private and only accessible to authorized project partners.[9]

More details on GitLab’s selection process for 5G-ROUTES can be found in D2.9 “Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0”.

Figure 4. 4 Code repository for the 5G-ROUTES project based on GitLab

4.6 Managing and Monitoring Technical Risks and Mitigating Actions

The domain of general risk management within the 5G-ROUTES project has been covered in D7.5 “Project Quality Handbook v1.0” and the Technical Manager has also taken this document as a basis for assessing technical risks.

According to D7.5 “Project Quality Handbook v1.0”, the role of risk management (RM) lies with the QRM who:

- coordinates the RM processes.
- keeps the risk register and the RM plan of the project up to date.
- advises partners on the different aspects of RM.
- performs project quality evaluation criteria, risk assessment, and continuous monitoring.
- based on the input received from respective task leaders, the QRM takes decisions regarding contingency plans in collaboration with the PM, that reviews and provides input to contingency plans.

One of the key roles of the TM regarding risk management is to support the actions of the QRM with technical background. At the time of writing this document, many critical risks have already been identified in the proposal and GA stages and within the first 6 months of the project. The most severe of these being the inability to design and deploy and 5G SA core before the first round of large-scale field trials. Still, the continuous identification of emerging risks will remain throughout the duration of the project to minimize the exposure to said risks.

From a technical standpoint, the ways of identifying project risks coincide with what has already been discussed in D7.5 “Project Quality Handbook v1.0”:

- initiative of the 5G-ROUTES partners, who can immediately notify the QRM if they have identified a particular risk. The QRM will get back to the partner and make sure that all required information is properly provided before qualitative analysis is undertaken for the identified risk.
- periodic 5G-ROUTES meetings, where risk identification may also be the focus of the meeting.
- meetings of the GeA and the PMB, whose agenda will include a report on quality and risk issues by the QRM.
- comparison with similar previous projects.
- analysis of WP or deliverable related risks.
- analysis of the work breakdown structure and the project timeline Gantt chart (e.g. identify issues on the critical path, identify periods where many tasks run in parallel, etc.).

In addition to the listed identification methods above, and considering what technical risks have been chalked up in the risk register⁵, the TM follows a few other specific potential risk factors:

- general market sentiment, meaning the supply capabilities of telco vendors. For example, the well-known issue of global chip shortage can lead to long delivery times for the planned hardware in the project.

⁵ The latest version (February 2022) of the risk register can be found in Annex IV

- SA core vendor activity. To be able to fulfil the project architecture as envisioned, much support is needed from the core vendor, specifically from the network and solution architects and engineers with thorough knowledge of the core and its functions.
- mobile network operator (MNO) internal work prioritization. This is relevant when deploying the RAN sites for the trials. With insufficient resources designated for 5G-ROUTES, there is a risk of not meeting the deadline of the first round of trials.
- coordination on technical issues between LMT and Telia. As with the previous bullet, this issue becomes critical when deploying the RAN sites since a roaming capable technical solution must be achieved.
- UE availability for trials. Doing large-scale field trials for CAM use cases requires the proper and suitable end user equipment (UE). Without these, there is a high risk of either not being able to achieve the desired KPIs or trialing the UCs at all.
- maturity of 3GPP R17 - As of February 2023, R17 is no longer in the scope of the 5G-ROUTES project due to its immaturity and thus all the corresponding risks are invalidated.

Keeping track of the risk mitigating actions within the project is the responsibility of the QRM and these actions are all reliant on the risk register. Therefore, it is the interest and duty of the TM to keep the register up to date and monitor it periodically. Mitigating each individual risk is done on a case-by-case method where a response plan is devised and eventually executed, and the residual and secondary risks are tracked to manage the outcomes of risk mitigating actions.

The latest risk register with the corresponding response plans can be found on the 5G-ROUTES SharePoint platform at all times.

5 Supporting Materials and Procedures

The following sub-chapters describe some of the core procedures and materials needed for the 5G-ROUTES project partners in their day-to-day operations. The materials presented belong to the domain of responsibility of the Technical Manager and are to be considered as guidelines as the specifics may, and in most cases, will change and evolve over time.

5.1 Tele-conferencing Procedures

5G-ROUTES partners meet several times throughout the project lifetime through both recurring and ad-hoc virtual meetings. For efficiency reasons, some of the recurrent meetings may be cancelled when their topics of discussion are covered in other meetings (e.g. WP leaders' meeting falls very close to a General Assembly meeting). The meetings in which the Technical Manager has actively been involved with are summarised in Table 5.1 below.

Table 5.1 Meetings with active Technical Manager involvement

Meeting type	Scope	Frequency	Participants
WP recurring meetings (virtual)	WP leader to control and monitor activities of tasks. Task and deliverable leaders to regularly communicate and align with the other participants or interlinked tasks/deliverables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1, weekly • WP2, weekly • WP3, weekly • WP4, ad-hoc⁶ • WP5, monthly • WP6, monthly 	For each WP: WP leader (chair), ongoing task participants, task participants of other interlinked WPs, WP leaders of other interlinked WPs.
WP leaders' meeting (virtual)	Manage the information flow with other WPs, monitor the WP plan and maintain consistency with the project plan.	Biweekly	Project Manager (chair), WP leaders, Project Coordinator, Technical Manager, invited project partners depending on the meeting agenda (e.g. Innovation and IPR Manager, Quality Manager, deliverable leader etc).
PMB meetings	Consortium management issues for the whole project, including technical matters, quality assurance, the consortium agreement, roles and responsibilities, audit certificates, ethics, gender issues, societal issues and liaison with 5G-PPP and other third parties and the EU.	Monthly	Project Coordinator (chair), Project Manager, Technical Manager, Innovation and IPR Manager, Quality Assurance and Risk Manager, Commercialisation Manager, Dissemination and Communication Manager.
General Assembly meetings (virtual and hybrid)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report by the Project Manager. • Report by the Quality Assurance & Risks Manager on quality and risks issues. 	Yearly	Project Coordinator (chair), representatives from each partner, having the authority to make decisions on behalf of their respective organisations in terms

⁶ At the time of writing as WP4 activities have only recently been kicked off

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reports by the WP Leaders on technical implementation issues. ● Approval of annual and final reports. ● Approval of yearly implementation plans. ● Decisions on specific items. 		of overall strategy and contractual aspects.
Project Architecture Task Force	Project architecture development.	Weekly	Technical Manager (chair), Deputy Technical Manager, representatives from key technical partners (mostly from WP2 and WP3).

In addition to the virtual technical and WP meetings organized on a regular basis, the TM has taken part in multiple consortium meetings which have been listed in Annex III⁷.

5.2 Project Architecture

Central to the successful completion of the field trials of 5G-ROUTES, and the project in general, is a collective understanding within the consortium on the complete technical solution being used. The mentioned collective understanding has been put together in the form of a project architecture. This entails not only the hardware and software delivered by specific vendors but also encompasses the efforts and results being made by project partners.

The current version of this deliverable (resubmission, written in January 2023) has seen many changes done to the PA compared to the version drafted in the early stages of 2022. The following sections reflect on the modifications while elaborating on the method of creating the project architecture and the involved parties. Additionally, this version addresses many initial comments made by the project reviewers from the European Commission.

5.2.1 Design Team and Process of Creation

In the process of creating the 5G-ROUTES project architecture, a modular approach has been used, where the 3GPP 5G architecture Option 2 with the Next Generation Core (NGC) has been chosen and the main parts of the complete 5G system are as follows:

- the 5G SA radio access network (RAN), consisting of Next Generation base stations called gNBs.
- the 5G SA core network (CN).
- the data network (DN).

The different network functions (NF) are operated in the core network which provides the base for network services as well as a common interface towards management and operation of the network.

⁷ As of December 2021

In the modular approach, as the name suggests, different parts of the project architecture have been presented as modules which are then described in more detail in specific deliverables dealing with those modules. The modules described are:

- the 5G SA core.
- management and orchestration (MANO).
- the 5G New Radio (NR) RAN.
- EDGE/MEC.
- the non-terrestrial network (NTN) backhubs. The NTN communication solution will follow the ETSI scenario A4 framework as described in ETSI TR 103 611 V1.1.1 (2020-06). This solution is offered for scenarios where the Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF) is not yet implemented. It is aimed as a back-up solution to the maritime use cases. The NTN communication will use an NTN (satellite) terminal and an NTN transport network.
- the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) Real-time kinematic (RTK) network location entity.
- the 5G-ROUTES use case devices. [10]

The 5G-ROUTES project architecture is focused on supporting advanced use cases and providing a platform for conducting large-scale field trials. To achieve this, the approach in developing the PA has been twofold. Firstly, the UC descriptions and their required KPIs have been used as a basis to develop the concept of the architecture. Keywords such as network coverage and mobility, architectural design, infrastructure dimensioning (including cloud and virtualization), hardware and software definitions, facility planning, services onboarding and evaluation/testing have all been considered.

Secondly, the following network elements and technologies which support the requirements towards the PA, have been identified and taken into consideration:

- physical hardware and infrastructure of the 5G system.
- the virtualized infrastructure, virtualized infrastructure managers (VIM), software defined networks (SDN).
- VIMs and MANO tools.
- monitoring and data analysis tools, KPIs and dashboards for visualization.
- technological enablers to support UCs (developed within the 5G-ROUTES project), application programming interfaces (API) for deploying and onboarding different services.

The creation of the project architecture has been a focused activity by a selected group of partners within the consortium, called together specifically for this assignment. This task force was initially led by the Technical Manager and supported heavily by the Deputy Technical Manager, however, as of Q4 2022 the effort has been spearheaded by TTU. As the vendor of the 5G SA core is EEE, they have been included in the creation process with regional project managers and group level solution engineers and architects. Additionally, from the consortium, telco operators were chosen to participate due to their specific knowledge and long-term experience on radio access networks. A few key partners from WP2, such as ATOS and CTTC have also played a major role in the PA's creation. The role of WP2 partners has been crucial as this is the work package where all the technological enablers have been developed.

5.2.2 First View of Project Architecture

As highlighted in previous sections, the 5G-ROUTES project architecture, depicted in Figure 5.1 (version 3, completed in September of 2023), is based on the 5G New Radio air interface and a standalone core network combination from EEE which includes two domains, called Domain A and Domain B, to account for cross-border scenarios. One domain is implemented in Latvia by LMT and the other domain is deployed by TTU in Estonia. The availability of two domains residing in two different countries allows for CAM cross-border services to be tested

in the 5G-ROUTES project through relevant CAM use cases. Details on these can be found in D1.1 “Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0” which describes the 5G-ROUTES CAM UCs and their respective scenarios. As TTU is an educational entity, for the purpose of 5G-ROUTES, it must be considered a virtual MNO with its own network code to be broadcasted on the air interface. The core network implements the 3GPP R15 and R16 functionalities.

The RAN will be based on the 5G NR gNBs, operating on 3.5 GHz and 24 GHz bands, and supplied by Ericsson. The 5G SA network in Latvia and Estonia will be running with similar configurations to ensure smooth integration and cross-border roaming functionalities. In an ideal situation the SA core supports a local breakout based roaming procedure to avoid extra delays introduced by a home routing-based roaming, hence benefitting from all the advantages of an edge site (i.e. short delay). However, there are uncertainties on the availability of the local breakout feature during the 5G-ROUTES project lifetime. Instead, a “disconnect and reconnect” procedure in the communication unit, emulating a session and service continuity (SSC) mode 3, plus IP traffic redirection will be explored during field trial execution to make a gateway change to address the proper entity’s instances (i.e., enablers, virtualized CAM service backends) available at each administrative domain.

The role of the core network, implemented on the Ericsson Cloud Native Infrastructure Solution (CNIS) platform, is to separate the control plane (CP) and the user plane (UP). Connectivity to the UP by any mobile user equipment is called a Protocol Data Unit (PDU) session and this session connects the UE through the gNB to the User Plain Function (UPF) at the CN and then eventually to the packet data network (PDN).

One of the key characteristics of the CN is network functions virtualization (NFV), which means that most of the CN’s nodes are virtualized as part of the NFV infrastructure. These nodes are not standalone devices but software processes running on virtual machines (VM) which in turn are set on top of commercial off the shelf (COTS) servers.

The 5G NR SA core is deployed in the CNIS in Riga and Tallinn where it is envisioned that a proprietary Ericsson Orchestrator (EO) solution will manage the 5G core NFs. EO Evolved Virtual Network Function (VNF) Management (EVNFM) module is used to support SOL001 and SOL004 artefacts. This solution, provided by Ericsson, is compliant with the 3GPP VNFs and containerized network functions (CNFs) and will be used to only deploy the set of NFs belonging to the 5G core, independently.

As described in D2.9 “Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0”, the PA is based on the 3GPP service-based architecture (SBA), running a modular framework where common applications are to be deployed using components with standard interfaces. Control plane functionalities of the 5G SA network are delivered via a set of interconnected network functions. NFs will be self-contained and will have either the role of a service consumer or that of a service producer as defined by the 3GPP SBA architecture.

Besides the cellular infrastructure, Figure 5.1 also includes the components being developed in WP2 and WP3 of 5G-ROUTES, namely the CAM service platform and the virtualized CAM service backends. The CAM service platform is constituted by the collection of technological enablers developed in the different tasks of WP2 (i.e. T2.1-T2.4) and the Tenant Web Portal element, presented in D2.7 “Tenant Web Portal Implementation and Deployment v1.0”. The enablers are designed to assist and provide complementary functionalities to the CAM services and they are not part of the 5G core procedures. Enablers and virtualized CAM services require to be packaged as cloud-native network services, as described in D2.9 “Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0”. These cloud-native network services can be deployed independently from the 5G core by an instance of the open source MANO (OSM) software, acting as a network functions virtualization orchestrator (NFVO), at the different points-of-presence (PoP) under its control. These PoPs are based on Kubernetes. The PoPs are local PDNs connected to the cellular infrastructure by means of a connection with the UPF NF of the deployed 5G SA core, which provides a local breakout point.

Figure 5. 1 High level project architecture for 5G-ROUTES (multi-domain, based on Valga/Valka test site deployment)

Figure 5. 21 In September 2023 new 5G SA core architecture was settled

The technological enablers developed at present in the scope of tasks T2.1, T2.2, T2.3 and T2.4 as part of WP2 are listed below:

- Resource allocation and positioning of V2X related NFs (T2.1 / D2.1).
- Low-latency cross-border synchronisation mechanism for seamless CAM service delivery (T2.1 / D2.1).
- Assisted Handover Algorithm for Cross-Domain CAM Service Provisioning (T2.1 / D2.1).
- V2X Message Routing Via MEC (T2.1 / D2.1).
- Cross-domain integration Fabric (T2.1 / D2.1).
- CAM repository (T2.1 / D2.1).
- Slice Negotiator (T2.2 / D2.3).
- Network Slicing for CAM Services (T2.2 / D2.3).
- 5G localization for VRU protection (T2.2 and T2.3 / D2.3 and D2.5).
- 5G network-based positioning and 5G integrated hybrid positioning (T2.3 / D2.5).
- Tenant Web Portal Dashboard (T2.4 / D2.7). [9]

The integration strategy for enablers plans to have them all onboarded to OSM and deployed before in the same NFVI where the virtualized CAM service backend will be deployed later because the aim of the enablers is to assist CAM services to, for instance, automate its deployment and provide continuity at the service level in cross-border situations. Indeed, the TWP will handle the onboarding of the CAM network service artefacts through the CAM Repository enabler and will trigger its instantiation with the help of the Integration Fabric enabler.

Instances of the different enablers constituting the CAM service platform can be distributed across the different points of presence available at each administrative domain. Thanks to this distributed deployment they can comply with constraints required by virtualized CAM service backends, for instance short latency provided by placing entities in an edge site close to the users. The suggested locations (edge, cloud core site) for the different enablers have been included in their respective descriptions in WP2 deliverables. Each administrative domain counts with its own instance of the 5G-ROUTES project architecture, which are interconnected so the different enablers at the different administrative domains can communicate and perform required negotiation and synchronization operations in cross-border situations. The availability of two MNOs residing in two different countries with their own CAM service platforms allows for CAM cross-border services to be tested in the framework of the 5G-ROUTES project through relevant CAM use cases. [9]

The Tenant Web Portal will be hosted in the cloud, acting as a common element for the connected administrative domains. Besides being the point for collecting and visualizing the data from the use case execution, the TWP will interact with the CAM Services Platform for orchestration purposes to:

- handle the onboarding of CAM network service artefacts through the CAM Repository enabler.
- trigger its instantiation/termination with the help of the Integration Fabric enabler.

It is worth noting that with this approach of a single TWP, there will only be the need to contact a single CAM Repository to onboard artefacts in all the different associated administrative domains, due to the synchronisation capabilities of the CAM Repository, and the service provider will decide in instantiation time in which administrative domain the CAM service will be deployed. [11]

As a final note on the PA, the 5G-ROUTES project is to implement location services through the GNSS RTK service with Ericsson Network Location Service (NLS). Ericsson's NLS will integrate the GNSS RTK service into the 5G SA core services as described in D2.5 "AI-based Positioning Enhancements for V2X v1.0". [12]

The 5G-ROUTES project architecture is a work in progress and is constantly evolving to reach its final version in D7.4 "Technical management handbook v2.0" by month 47.

5.3 High Level Performance Measurement Framework

Innovation projects on network industries should harmonize their terminology, requirements, and methods for monitoring and reporting performance to increase their transparency, productivity and efficiency and reduce the total societal cost of maintaining and modernizing the networks. Even though every project is unique and with different key factors, the methodology and approach in creating a suitable performance measurement framework is unified. It is important to state, however, that harmonization does not mean that the performance indicators and their formulas should be identical across industries and projects.

5.3.1 The Indicators Used

The first step in the process is the identification of the various indicators used by different companies in network industries and across sectors. In the 5G-ROUTES project, a review was conducted to gather the information about the performance indicator systems in different work packages, including requirements, measurement, monitoring, assessment and evaluation of indicators. This was done to put in place the hierarchy of indicators and show how the results should be collected in similar, systematic ways and calculated in the TWP. The next step was to model the indicators in a single framework as shown in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5. 3 Performance measurement framework in the 5G-ROUTES project

The following types of KPIs can be identified in the 5G-ROUTES project:

- **Network level performance indicators (PI)**, which are agnostic to the use cases. The targets for these network PIs are calculated so that the use case target PIs can be fulfilled. These PIs and their measurements are described in D1.5 “Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0”. The results of the measurements and the evaluation will be reported in D3.2 “Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM v2.0”. The KPIs will be selected from the measured performance indicators and described in D1.6 “Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v2.0”.
- specific **technical KPIs**. Starting from the data collected during the use case trials, PIs for assessing the technical performance at service level are calculated, such as latencies of the different legs of the 5G delivery

chain. The value of the PI may depend on the configuration of the 5G network, the enablers used and potential environmental variables (such as weather) and situational variables, such as the speed of the vehicles. Special attention will also be put on the effect of border crossing and handover.

PIs, which are identified as important for the evaluation of the technical performance of the use case, are fed as KPIs into the Tenant Web Portal. These indicators are compared to threshold values, set in D1.9 “Use Cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0”, and provide the satisfaction level of the performance indicators. The satisfaction levels of different indicators are then combined to form a composite indicator, which represents the satisfaction level for the use case, and these are visualized in the Tenant Web Portal.

The technical PIs are mainly calculated from measured data, but data from user feedback is used to some extent, e.g. for the Quality of Experience (QoE) KPI. The framework for collecting and analyzing the data is described in D1.12 “Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0”, section 3.3.

The results of the evaluation during the different trial phases will be reported in D4.6 “Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned v1.0”, D4.7 “Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned v2.0”, and D4.8 “Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned final version”.

- **Business KPIs**, which are calculated from input provided by end users during use case trials and from stakeholder interactions, such as focus groups and interviews. The framework for business validation is described in D1.12 “Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0”, section 3.4. The results of the business assessment evaluation will be reported in all final WP5 deliverables but mainly in D5.2 “Commercialization and marketing plan for 5G enabled business models for CAN final version” and in D5.3 “Report on impact assessment and cost-benefit analysis v1.0”.

The fragment of the performance evaluation framework can be seen in Figure 5.3

Figure 5. 4 Fragment of the performance measurement framework in the 5G-ROUTES project

The 5G-ROUTES project is assessing the MNO performance from the network side and the business impact to the MNO as seen in Figure 5. 5. It is important to note here that the key factor for business impact is ultimately the interruption time when the use case is moving from one administrative domain to the other (i.e. crossing the border from Estonia to Latvia or vice versa). This process of crossing the border causes a disruption in connectivity which in turn affects all the listed PIs (latency, jitter, reliability, etc) and eventually the perceived quality of the service.

Based on these requirements, the required performance with the PIs of the network is derived in D1.5 “Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0”. Those PIs will be measured for assessing the readiness of the 5G network for the use cases. From those PIs the KPIs can be selected, if decided so in the next phases of the project and can be described in D1.6 “Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v2.0”.

The 5G network level PIs have been selected to validate the network features and confirm that the network is able to provide the service needed for the use cases to be tested. The sources of the PI definitions are the NGMN 5G Trial and Testing Initiative Pre-Commercial Network Trials Framework Definition, ITU-R M.2410-0, 5G PPP Phase II KPI definitions, other 5G-PPP projects and 3GPP documents. The Network PIs defined in these documents are used to provide a performance evaluation of 5G systems and should be tested on 3GPP R16. However, as described in section 3.3 of this document, R17. Network level PIs are the requirements for 5G network to ensure the high-level communication between the users and infrastructure in the use cases. Such PIs include interruption time on the border, data rate, handover time, latency, jitter, connection density, reliability, positioning accuracy, coverage and availability.

Figure 5. 5 MNO performance assessment

5.3.2 Business Impact Validation

The business validation process in 5G-ROUTES is challenged with engaging and examining the field trials with a commercial and business lens to identify those solutions that are most likely to become commercially viable and can deliver the most immediate quantifiable value to the stakeholders involved in each use case. The overall methodology adopted has many key activities and actions to ultimately arrive at providing practical commercial recommendations to the consortium:

- create a detailed assessment of broad market opportunities and the evolving technological, financial and social environment surrounding each 5G-ROUTES use-case.
- undertake an analysis of the services and players, their roles, and relationships within the added value structure in challenging multi-MNO, multi-vendor, cross terrestrial-satellite, cross-border scenarios to specifically examine the value needs/benefit for each stakeholder in each use-case.
- perform impact assessments and cost-benefit analyses of dedicated and validated 5G architecture and cooperative, connected and automated mobility (CCAM) to justify commercially the technologies and the deployment investments, whilst addressing the social and environmental impact.
- consolidate 5G-ROUTES use cases into 3 targeted cluster groups of applications (i.e. automotive, infotainment services and multimodal transport & logistics services) that can be delivered to the market as bundled commercial services.

- assign each commercial service with a lead commercialization partner around whom the business development plan, that is created within 5G-ROUTES, can be centered.
- identify and protect key commercially differentiating innovation with patents that allows the output from 5G-ROUTES to be competitively differentiated on the global market.
- expand each commercial service sufficiently to understand key dynamics around revenue, cost and investment for each commercial cluster and ultimately prepare a business plan for potential implementation post project completion.

The end goal for the business validation process is to create anticipatory business plans for the 3 previously mentioned targeted cluster groups of applications. The knowledge gained to support those business initiatives is strongly grounded in the use cases that are examined within 5G-ROUTES and hence we have chosen a customer-focused, collaborative and iterative process that helps guide the use cases from initial ideas through to potential business impact and demonstrate how commercial actors supporting the pilots could move those outputs closer to commercial reality.

5.3.3 Performance Assessment

In D1.9 “Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0”, KPIs have been defined to assess the performance of the use cases while considering throughput, latency, reliability, capacity and localization from a technical and cross border point of view.

Several use cases illustrating the interest of 5G networks have been defined in the 5G-ROUTES project with each use case having particular requirements towards the 5G infrastructure. To validate the benefits of 5G and the technical enablers for each use case, a certain number of cross border test scenarios will be executed during the 5G-ROUTES project to assess the behavior of the system in critical situations:

- network load.
- mobility situation.
- with/without certain technical enablers.
- with different releases.

The analysis of the test scenarios will be based on technical KPIs. KPIs are indicators representative of the most important aspects of a use case. The complete process flow for data collection and processing is illustrated in Figure 5.5. The data, stored in the TWP, will be the basis for the assessment of the technical performance of the use case and enablers while the results will be reported in task T4.3 of the project. Based on the results of the trials and the evaluation assessment, changes may be performed to the use case before the next iteration of the trials.

Figure 5. 6 Process of collecting and processing data

The use case performance assessment can be seen in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.7 Use-case performance assessment

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Extended indicators

During the lab tests and field trials, use case leaders will collect raw measurements. A raw measurement is for example the latency or the throughput over time. In the case of data transfer, raw measurements could be for example given by the packets' time stamps. These raw measurements are then analyzed by the use case leaders to generate indicators or metrics:

- time series will for example be used to compute the mean, max and min delay. The time series is the raw measurement from which mean, max and min delay indicators are extracted.
- analyzing the time stamps could be used to estimate the 95 percentiles of packets below a threshold. The time stamp records are the raw measurements, the 95 percentiles of packets below the threshold is the indicator.

Complex systems are composed of different sub-systems and some measurements that are needed to assess if a use case cannot be realized, either because the technology is not there or because the measurement campaign is too complex to be done in the project. To cope with this issue, 5G-ROUTES has defined extended indicators. Extended indicators can include raw measurements, but also specification or any justification document needed to justify the value of the extended indicator:

- evaluation of the localization accuracy requires the ability to compare the information coming from a Global Positioning System (GPS) signal to the real position. In practice, this comparison requires specific measurement equipment to consider the trajectory of the vehicles, localization accuracy will be estimated based on GPS, RTK or light detection and ranging (LIDAR) specifications and used to assess the corresponding Status PI.
- the impact on the capacity of a new radio resource management (RRM) algorithm or new bearer type requires to set up load tests. These tests cannot be realized in 5G-ROUTES and the benefit can only be estimated based on the experience of previous optimizations.

6 Conclusions

D7.3 “Technical Management Handbook v1.0” outlines the core procedures performed in the realm of technical management to ensure a smooth and efficient implementation of the 5G-ROUTES project. It also furnishes supporting material to enable a uniform treatment of the key processes and concepts. The deliverable is meant to support all the consortium members, throughout the project’s duration.

As with all projects, the successful completion of 5G-ROUTES depends on efficient and well-structured project management procedures and technical management is a subset of these. It is important to note that guaranteeing the quality within the project is a collective endeavor among all partners, particularly in the case of technical deliverables, which serve as the foundation for the rest of the project. Adhering to the guidelines presented in this handbook will ensure the timely completion of technically sound deliverables, which are appropriately linked to corresponding deliverables. Additionally, any issues that arise can be identified early enough to be addressed in cooperation with the necessary partners.

During the first year of the 5G-ROUTES project, the most difficult tasks, from a technical management point of view, have been to:

- identify the partners who need to be involved in specific tasks, and who also have the necessary knowhow.
- familiarize all the project partners with 5G as a technology.
- find the balance between being too technical and not technical enough with different audiences.
- not overload non-essential partners with technical issues.

All-in-all, this deliverable will enable better coordination and collaboration between the consortium partners and will prevent possible deviations from the intended project work plan. The present document is the initial version, where the overall management structure of 5G-ROUTES is presented, and more focus has been directed at technical management. On month 45 of the project, a final version will be provided, discussing the implementation of the proposed guidelines, the arisen issues and the lessons learned.

7 References

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- [12] D2.5 AI-based Positioning Enhancements for V2X v1.0

Annex I: Consortium Members

Abbreviation	Full name and country of origin
EEE	ERICSSON EESTI AS, Estonia
ADS	AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE GMBH, Germany
ADSF	AIRBUS DEFENCE AND SPACE SAS, France
PV	AKCIJU SABIEDRIBA PASAZIERU VILCIENS, Latvia
ATOS	ATOS SPAIN SA, Spain
BRA	BRAINSTORM MULTIMEDIA SL, Spain
CTTC	CENTRE TECNOLOGIC DE TELECOMUNICACIONS DE CATALUNYA, Spain
EBOS	EBOS TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED, Cyprus
EVR	EESTI RAUDTEE AS, Estonia
ENIDE	ENIDE SOLUTIONS .S.L, Spain
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS, Greece
ILS	INLECOM INNOVATION ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA, Greece
VED	INSTITUT VEDECOM, France
IQU	IQUADRAT INFORMATICA SL, Spain
LMT	LATVIJAS MOBILAIS TELEFONS SIA, Latvia
SWM	SWARCO MIZAR SRL, Italy
TTU	TALLINNA TEHNIKAULIKOOL, Estonia
VTT	Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy, Finland
TELIA	TELIA EESTI AS, Estonia
VEDIA	VEDIAFI OY, Finland
WINGS	WINGS ICT SOLUTIONS INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IKE, Greece
EDI	ELEKTRONIKAS UN DATORZINATNU INSTITUTS

Annex II: List of Deliverables⁸

D#	Deliverable name	WP #	Lead participant	Type	DL	Delivery date (in months)
D1.1	Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v1.0	1	ADS	R	PU	4
D1.2	Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM final		ADS	R	PU	35
D1.3	Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v1.0		LMT	R	PU	4
D1.4	Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies final		LMT	R	PU	35
D1.5	Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM v1.0		TELIA	R	PU	4
D1.6	Methodologies for cross-border collaboration and validation of 5G features for CAM final		TELIA	R	PU	36
D1.7	Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v1.0		VTT	R	PU	3
D1.8	Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results final		VTT	R	PU	36
D1.9	Use cases, scenarios, specs & target KPIs for 5G for CAM v2.0		ADS	R	PU	16
D1.10	Report on 5G-ROUTES CAM deployment plan and longer-term deployment strategies v2.0		LMT	R	PU	10
D1.12	Testing framework for the technological and business validation and benchmarking of the results v2.0		VTT	R	PU	16
D1.13	Analysis of multi-hop solutions broadening 5G connection coverage at sea between vessels and shore		LMT	R	PU	45
D2.1	AI assisted cross-domain MEC and integration fabric for CAM services v1.0		2	CTTC	R	CO
D2.2	AI assisted cross-domain MEC and integration fabric for CAM services v2.0	CTTC		R	CO	35

⁸ According to the latest 5G-ROUTES amendment draft

D2.3	AI-based end-to-end slicing optimisation and innovative spectrum usage for CAM services v1.0		WINGS	R	CO	8
D2.4	AI-based end-to-end slicing optimisation and innovative spectrum usage for CAM services v2.0		WINGS	R	CO	35
D2.5	AI-based positioning enhancements for V2X v1.0		TTU	R	CO	8
D2.6	AI-based positioning enhancements for V2X v2.0		TTU	R	CO	35
D2.7	Tenant Web Portal implementation and deployment v1.0		EBOS	OTHER	CO	8
D2.8	Tenant Web Portal implementation and deployment v2.0		EBOS	OTHER	CO	35
D2.9	Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v1.0		ATOS	R	PU	9
D2.10	Report on integration and testing of technological enablers for CAM v2.0		ATOS	R	PU	36
D3.1	Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM v1.0		TELIA	R	PU	9
D3.2	Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM v2.0		TELIA	R	PU	30
D3.3	Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v1.0		EDI	R	PU	9
D3.4	Report on CAM infrastructure development in vehicles, railways and maritime v2.0		EDI	R	PU	36
D3.5	Report on integration of technological enablers with MNOs 5G infrastructure and incremental upgrades v1.0		LMT	R	PU	38
D3.6	Report on integration of technological enablers with MNOs 5G infrastructure and incremental upgrades v2.0	3	LMT	R	PU	40
D3.7	Report on integration of technological enablers with MNOs 5G infrastructure and incremental upgrades final version		LMT	R	PU	45
D3.8	Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness v1.0		VTT	R	PU	20
D3.9	Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness v2.0		VTT	R	PU	31
D3.10	Report on lab trials findings and field trials operational readiness final		VTT	R	PU	43
D3.11	Report on 5G infrastructure setup for CAM final		TELIA	R	PU	40

D4.1	LL planning, setup, operational management handbook v1.0	4	BRA	R	PU	18
D4.2	LL planning, setup, operational management handbook v2.0		BRA	R	PU	30
D4.3	5G CAM field trials v1.0		EEE	DEM	PU	27
D4.4	5G CAM field trials v2.0		EEE	DEM	PU	39
D4.5	5G CAM field trials final version		EEE	DEM	PU	45
D4.6	Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned v1.0		IQU	R	PU	28
D4.7	Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned v2.0		IQU	R	PU	40
D4.8	Report on performance evaluation and lessons learned final version		IQU	R	PU	46
D4.9	LL planning, setup, operational management handbook final		BRA	R	PU	40
D5.1	Commercialisation and marketing plan for 5G enabled business models for CAM v1.0	5	ILS	R	CO	7
D5.2	Commercialisation and marketing plan for 5G enabled business models for CAM final version		ILS	R	CO	46
D5.3	Report on impact assessment and cost-benefit analysis v1.0		CERTH	R	PU	21
D5.4	Report on impact assessment and cost-benefit analysis final version		CERTH	R	PU	44
D5.5	Innovation management plan and IP protection report v1.0		ILS	R	CO	18
D5.6	Innovation management plan and IP protection report final version		ILS	R	CO	45
D5.7	Data Management Plan v1.0		EBOS	ORDP	PU	6
D5.8	Data Management Plan final version		EBOS	ORDP	PU	45
D5.9	Report on standardisation activities and spectrum allocation recommendations v1		EEE	R	PU	5
D5.10	Report on standardisation activities and spectrum allocation recommendations final version		EEE	R	PU	45

D6.1	Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v1.0	6	CTTC	R	PU	5
D6.2	Dissemination & Communication plans and activities v2.0		CTTC	R	PU	28
D6.3	Dissemination & Communication plans and activities final version		CTTC	R	PU	48
D6.4	Project website and social media presence		EBOS	DEC	PU	1
D6.5	Information package for external SMEs to facilitate the design of new CAM applications v1.0		WINGS	R	PU	16
D6.6	Information package for external SMEs to facilitate the design of new CAM applications final version		WINGS	R	PU	44
D6.7	Report on joint planning activities with 5G-PPP		ATOS	R	PU	22
D6.8	Report on technical, business, security, privacy, policies and regulatory recommendations v1.0		ILS	R	PU	34
D6.9	Final recommendations and summary of joint activities with the 5G PPP		ILS	R	PU	48
D7.1	Project activity reports v1.0	7	EEE	R	CO	17
D7.2	Project activity reports final version		EEE	R	CO	48
D7.3	Technical management handbook v1.0		TELIA	R	PU	15
D7.4	Technical management handbook final version		TELIA	R	PU	47
D7.5	Project Quality Handbook v1.0		ENIDE	R	CO	2
D7.6	Project Quality Handbook final version		ENIDE	R	CO	48
D7.7	Report on legal and ethics monitoring v1.0		TTU	R	PU	3
D7.8	Report on legal and ethics monitoring final version		TTU	R	PU	47
D8.1	H - Requirement No. 1	8	EEE	ETHICS	CO	6
D8.2	POPD - Requirement No. 2		EEE	ETHICS	CO	6

Annex III: WP Leaders', PMB and GeA Meetings

Meeting Title	Place	Dates	Scope
Kick-off Meeting	Virtual	16-17 Sep 2020	To establish a common vision for the project. To communicate contributions and expectations from each partner. To discuss the approach, management structure and critical milestones. To explain contractual and administrative duties and reporting procedures. To agree on action plan for next 6 months per working group and for the whole project.
PMB meeting 1 (Planned)	Virtual	17 Nov 2020	Discussing project progress Raising any risks and identifying mitigation actions
Plenary 2 (Ad Hoc)	Virtual	8 Dec 2020	Organise participation in 5G for CAM in cross-border Corridors meeting. Technical Progress and Trials Preparation. 5G-PPP Participation (ATOS). Progress overview - Deliverables Progress. Project coordination matters – reorganisation. Reporting (WPs & Financial Management).
Plenary 3 (Planned)	Virtual	11 Jan 2021	To discuss project progress and urgent matters needing attention. To finalise Amendment 1. To discuss Technical Progress and Trials Preparation.
PMB meeting 2 (Planned)	Virtual	3 Mar 2021	To discuss project progress. To raise any risks and identify mitigation actions.
Plenary 4 (Ad-hoc)	Virtual	29 Apr 2021	To update partners regarding 5G core risk and potential solutions and align views. Prepare for the interim review.
PMB meeting (Ad-hoc)	Virtual	14 May 2021	To discuss 5G core risk and rail case resources issue. (invited partners LMT and TTU). Evaluate alternative options.
Follow up PMB meeting (Ad-hoc)	Virtual	21 May 2021	To evaluate optimal 5G core network solution.
PMB meeting 3 (Planned)	Virtual	25 Jun 2021	Reaching a decision on the 5G Core to finalise our implementation plan and send a completed report to the PO.

Meeting Title	Place	Dates	Scope
PMB meeting (Ad-hoc)	Virtual	29 Jun 2021	Reach a decision on the 5G Core to finalise our implementation plan and send a completed report to the PO; WP1 deliverable delays and revised delivery plan; Comments on the Risk Register.
PMB meeting 4 (Planned)	Virtual	7 Sep 2021	Agree on the need and feasibility of a face 2 face meeting; Arrive at an action plan and assign clear responsibilities for addressing each EC review recommendation; Initiate the discussion about the amendment; Agree on any other open issues.
WP leaders meeting 1	Virtual	10 Sep 2021	Inform WP leaders about the action plan agreed in the PMB meeting on 7/9 about how to address the Review comments; Initiate the discussion about the amendment; Brainstorming about how to further strengthen the collaboration and flow of information between the WPs;
WP leaders meeting 2	Virtual	24 Sep 2021	Update from the Technical Manager about the project architecture design status; Update about where we are with the addressing of the EC review recommendations; Clarify the plan for the submission of rejected deliverables and the amendment.
WP leaders meeting 3	Virtual	8 Oct 2021	Update from the Technical Manager about the project architecture design status; Discussion about project extension (pros and cons of different options); Finalisation of the General Assembly meeting agenda.
Annual GeA Meeting	Tallin, Estonia (Hybrid)	19-20 Oct 2021	To present the status of WP activities and action plans for interim review recommendations. Reach a common understanding about timeline and scope changes including core setup. Perform voting about the extension of the project duration (by how many months and under what conditions).
WP leaders meeting 4	Virtual	5 Nov 2021	Presentation of the new process for deliverables' preparation and submission by the Quality Manager; Planning for the submission of deliverables (new and rejected) until the end of the year; Agreement on final planning for the description of the project architecture.
WP leaders meeting 5	Virtual	12 Nov 2021	Status of project architecture; New deliverable review procedure; Status of deliverables due by the end of this year.

Meeting Title	Place	Dates	Scope
WP leaders meeting 6	Virtual	26 Nov 2021	PO feedback for amendment and pending deliverables; Status of ongoing deliverables.

Annex IV: Risk Register of 5G-ROUTES

Risk Number	WP	Risk Description	Risk category	Risk Owner	Potential impact on project	Inherent risk score (P, I, Total (Pxl))	Risk responses	Residual risk score after risk response (P, I, Total (Pxl))	Comments
1	2,3	High expectations for software capabilities: All system components must be finely tuned, reliable and scalable to achieve the required KPIs that exceed usual TRL 8 solutions.	AD - Supplier risk	TTU, LMT	The system components do not achieve the expected TRL.	3 2 6	The technological enablers and the 5G CAM infrastructure will be configurable, performant and scalable. Security and privacy will be considered and enforced all the way through design and implementation. The consortium includes partners with sound experience in setting up such solutions.	0	This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement.

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2	1,2,3,4	Less than expected performance: The risk is that if the 5G CAM ecosystem fails to match required performance indicators, the solution acceptability and usefulness is adversely affected.	AD - Process risk	TELIA, TTU, LMT, EEE	The system does not achieve the KPIs.	2	4	8	The performance objectives of each use case will be properly captured in requirements producing all the appropriate technology and application extensions, solution optimisations and tuning so that reliable performance impact indicators are produced. This risk materialised in WP1 and was addressed with more interim deliverables.		0	This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement.
3	1,4	Requirements capture: There is a risk that requirements were not well defined, therefore, there is no reference to	AD - Process risk	TELIA, EEE	The project solutions do not have a clear reference point for their performance.	2	4	8	The requirements are methodologically captured in WP1 and in the trials with end-users playing a key role. The project evolution process		0	This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement.

		track requirements and validate KPIs.							is agile, and the solution adapts to changing user requirements during the lifetime of the project. This risk materialised in WP1 and was addressed with more interim deliverables.			
4	4,5	KPI framework complexity: There are risks related to meeting the KPIs during field trials due to a non harmonized treatment of KPIs among the partners of the consortium.	AD - Process risk	EEE, ILS. Monitored by the ILS.	Lack of understanding of use cases from business perspective. The project solution does not meet the market needs.	2	2	4	The execution of use case trials will undergo an iterative feedback-loop process of validating the KPIs against different 3GPP releases. Improvements will be made after each testing cycle, evaluating the success of meeting the target KPI values. The forward planning strategy of 5G-ROUTES minimises this			This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement.

		are below the required level of maturity to sustain the difficult application requirements, requiring specialised customised development to achieve the appropriate TRL for their deployment in the field trials.							Portal, are project assets or belong to live developments and/or platform solutions (e.g. EEE, ADS, BRA, VED, etc). The risk minimises as 5G-ROUTES will perform incremental development, configuration, integration and extension of such components. For all solutions, there will be alternatives and options, producing less risky implementations properly tested before deployment. Risk is monitored by TM.			Agreement.
7	1,2,3	Data and information security: The risk concerns	TC - Information security risk	TELIA, TTU, LMT. Monitore	Data breach, disclosure of confidential information, etc.	3	4	1 2	The 5G infrastructure and the Tenant Web Portal			This risk was identified in the

		the security and privacy of data and information, as security is of utmost importance in 5G-ROUTES.		d by TELIA.					comprises of services for encryption, authorisation, pseudo-anonymisation and secure information flows. These will be protected behind a secured access environment with appropriate security policies. Risk monitored by the TM.			Grant Agreement.
8	3,4	Testing issues: The risk that testing on the deployed 5G CAM ecosystem during large-scale field trials will not yield to obtaining the expected outcomes.	TC - technical risk	LMT, EEE. Monitored by the ILS and ENIDE.	Delayed validation, impossibility to reach KPIs	3	2	6	Testing of the CAM use cases will initially be conducted in lab trials (local, integration and system) over 3 different 5G testbeds before validation in actual large-scale field trials. Testing is a part of the quality assurance function and is			This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement. The probability of this risk increased due to COVID-19.

									monitored by the PM and QRM when providing the final quality check on deliverables. Multiple iterations in the lab trials work as mitigating action. Testing and validation might be negatively affected by the travel restrictions imposed due to COVID-19. Some mitigation could be achieved by the exceptions to travel restrictions based on professional reasons, as well as the potential extension of the project after the COVID-19 emergency.			
9	2,3	Reliability issues: The risk is that the developed 5G	TC - technical risk	TTU, LMT. Monitore	Delayed field trials, impossibility to reach the KPIs	1	4	4	The developed system uses advanced software			This risk was identified in the

		CAM ecosystem will not be reaching the proper availability and reliability status as required to meet the field trials' needs.		d by TELIA.					development tools, such as virtualisation and container-based deployment of services. This technology risk is addressed via integration of components and tested using existing software resources, also using cloud deployment via container technology. Risk monitored by the TM.			Grant Agreement.
10	2,3,4	Interoperability: There is a risk that the system developed will not be compatible and not be able to be packaged together with the commercial 5G and CAM	TC - technical risk	TTU, LMT, EEE. Monitored by TELIA.	Difficulty in reaching the market	3	2	6	The risk is addressed by technology, where common standards for data representations are adopted, APIs are constructed for all solutions, and 'dockerisation', 'compartmentation' and			This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement.

		infrastructure to form a unified 5G CAM ecosystem.							virtualisation are used for deploying and delivering the system in the cloud. Both the probability and the impact of such a risk will be monitored and controlled by the TM.			
11	4	Large-scale complexity: The number of use cases and the KPIs of the use cases in the field trials place significant configuration requirements to the setup environment.	AD - Process risk	EEE. Monitored by TELIA.	The environment does not achieve the KPIs.	2	4	8	WP7 is closely following the progress in the field trials and the basic technology developments. The system provides configurable connectivity and individual security policies for accessing and delivering information. Risk is constantly monitored by the TM.			This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement.

12	1,2,3,4,7	Lack of coordination: In large projects there is a risk related to ad hoc and uncoordinated development, resulting in diverging results and components.	PM - Managerial risk	ILS, TELIA, TTU, LMT, EEE. Monitored by TELIA and ENIDE.	Divergent results incompatible with the unified objectives of the project.	3	4	1 2	5G-ROUTES will use an agile methodology. All developments are incremental with end-users directly collaborating to the development of the system components. The development approach and progress are constantly monitored by the TM and managed by the QRM, when providing the final quality check on deliverables. This risk materialised in year 1 of the project, therefore ILS proposed monthly WP leaders meetings and cross-WP workshops in individual WP recurrent meetings. Lack of technical				This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement.
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									coordination due to missing Technical manager also materialised in year 2. EEE and TELIA held regular meetings as a mitigation action.				
13	1,2,3,4,7	Technology Management, Late Identification of Issues: The risk is about technology issues and defects, or possibly wrong options are only discovered at a very late stage of the project creating high risks to execution or inability to perform.	PM - Managerial risk	TELIA, TTU, LMT, EEE.	Unsufficient time and resources, potential inability to perform.	3	4	1 2	The project plan is agile and adaptive, leaving sufficient space for adaptation and rework if necessary. Project planning allows controlling such risks, through a separate planning process and dedicated roles for the project and for the field trials. This was detected by the PM and mitigated thanks to dedicated meetings				This risk was identified in the Grant Agreement. Mitigation actions took place in Spring 2021.

									(General Assembly and PMBs in April and May 2021).				
14	4	A use case is not completed: The risk is not to have a use case executed because of lack of resources and/or personnel changes from a project partner.	PM - Managerial risk	EEE	Potential impact on interdependencies of use cases.	3	4	1 2	The PM will raise the issue urgently with the management of the partner organisation, as losing one of the use cases may decrease the quality of the outcome of the project. If no alternative pilot can be found within the consortium, in consultation with the EC, the consortium will consider a replacement pilot (and maybe partner). The risk of not completing a use case because of insufficient resources was detected by the				This risk was detected and addressed in spring 2021.

									PM in Spring 2021 and mitigated thanks to dedicated meetings (General Assembly and PMBs in April and May 2021).				
15	4,5	Risks to innovation capacity building: Risk that technology developments are constrained in the 'closed world' of individual researchers, thereby delivering solutions of limited scope and applicability.	AD - Institutional risk	ILS/eBOS	Solutions are of limited scope and applicability.	2	4	8	There will be a strong innovation, capacity building and commercialisation drive in the project. There is strong industrial, research and SME participation in the project. The TM and IM constantly monitor this risk.				
16	All	Partners engagement, mitigation in the event of partners not	PM - Managerial risk	ILS (WP5 leader)	Delayed tasks and deliverables, unmet KPIs	3	8	24	The consortium has strong R&D delivery capacity. Partners' skills fully cover needs.				The probability and impact of this risk

		<p>performing or exiting the project: Partner problems (e.g. underperforming partner; or a key partner having a key role leaves the project; disagreements or loss of interest).</p>							<p>Care has been taken, so that all important technical tasks have an overlap in shared knowledge amongst partners, and there are always options and support to cover up for the work planned between partners. WP leaders monitor progress at WP level and communicate difficulties to PM. However, exit of one of the partners, especially one having a key role in the project would be a serious setback. The PC will take immediate actions to find a replacement partner within or outside the</p>				<p>increased due to the COVID-19 pandemic.</p>
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									consortium. The possibility of engaging partners in physical meetings has been hindered by the travel restrictions imposed by COVID-19, therefore more virtual meetings have been taken place as a mitigation action.			
17	7	Project execution risks (e.g. critical deliverables are delayed or poor quality).	PM - Schedule risk	EEE	Possible delay in work plan.	3	8	2 4	Strong dependency analysis. Quality procedures, templates and guidelines are key elements for mitigating this risk. WP leaders will carry out detailed monitoring of tasks, with specific attention to the dependencies. EuresTools will be used by each			The probability and impact of this risk increased due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

									partner. If there is a delay with one task, the knock-on effects can be quickly checked, and contingencies put in place to manage time slippage. This risk materialised within T5.4 and was addressed with more internal meetings among the task leader and the contributors. It also materialised in WP1 and was addressed with more interim deliverables.			
18	All	5G SA core network setup: Unavailability of 5G core network as per initial GA plan impacting trials implementation. Anticipated	TC - technical risk	TELIA	<p>More time and budget needed. Potential risk to stop the project before its natural conclusion.</p> <p>As of February 2023 the 5G SA cores for TTU and LMT have been procured and their deployment is ongoing. Still, the risk of unexpected</p>	4	4	16	Mitigation strategy is included in amendment 2. A 12 months extension is envisioned as a measure allowing time for the setup of the 5G			This risk was unforeseen in the Grant Agreement.

		delay 12 months.			technical/integration/functionality issues remains.				core infrastructure and the release of the new versions of standards for the trials roll out. Another mitigation action is the standalone core technology from EEE. Different technical workarounds are considered to be the mitigating action against any core integration or functionality issues.			
19	All	Quality management: deliverables lack technical depth	PM - managerial risk	ENIDE	Technical results do not match the project ambition. This could have an impact on the technologies available to the use cases and the trials.	3	4	1 2	This risk materialised during the first year of the project. ENIDE proposes to improve the enforcement of the quality management methodology			The mitigation action was launched following the first review by the PO.

									with a mandatory review by the PC, TC, and PM in the deliverable review procedure. The deliverable template, peer review template, and D7.5 were updated accordingly.			
20	All	Risk management: late identification of risks and/or ineffective mitigation	PM - Managerial risk	ENIDE	Weak mitigation leading to inability to overcome issues.	3	4	1 2	This risk materialised during the first year of the project. ENIDE proposes to improve the enforcement of the risk management methodology with a) an updated deliverable review template that allows the monthly identification of risks in new deliverables b) a mandatory			The mitigation action was launched following the first review by the PO.

